

Event metadata

Event title	Our Future Health: A world-leading platform for discovery, aetiological and translational research
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	31/03/2026
Time of event	12pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Our Future Health is the world's largest prospective cohort study, designed to recruit 5 million participants in the UK to enable researchers to find new ways to prevent, detect, and treat diseases. To date, over 2.5 million adults have consented to share their health records and lifestyle data, providing a resource of unrivalled scale and statistical precision for the life sciences.</p> <p>This webinar offers a unique opportunity to learn about the types of data available to researchers and hear key insights gained from building a research cohort of such unprecedented scale. We will explore how genetic data is generated and curated, and how it is made accessible through the Our Future Health Trusted Research Environment.</p> <p>Dr Ryan Arathimos will share his experience in overseeing the ongoing genotyping of study participants and designing the genotype array. He will also discuss how the program facilitates sample access and recontact studies to drive translational research excellence.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/our-future-health-uk-2026
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	otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Genomics http://edamontology.org/topic_0622
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians interested in large-scale cohort data, statistical genetics, and translational research.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the context of the Our Future Health UK project and how to apply for access to the data
Speakers	Dr Ryan Arathimos, Senior Statistical Geneticist, Our Future Health UK
Training materials	Materials shared in this Zenodo record: Our Future Health AustralianBiocommons Mar 2026.pdf: slides presented during the webinar Materials shared elsewhere: Note that this webinar was not recorded at the request of Our Future Health.
Related material	Cohort profile: https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyaf171 Publication: https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03438-0